
The meteorology of Gale Crater as determined from Rover Environmental Monitoring Station observations and numerical modeling. Part II: Interpretation

Scot C.R. Rafkin^{a,*}, Jorge Pla-Garcia^{a,b}, Melinda Kahre^c, Javier Gomez-Elvira^b, Victoria E. Hamilton^a, Mercedes Marín^c, Sara Navarro^c, Josefina Torres^b, Ashwin Vasavada^d

^aSouthwest Research Institute, Boulder, CO, 80302, United States

^bCentro de Astrobiología, Torrejón de Ardoz, Spain

^cNASA Ames Research Center, Moffett Field, CA 94035, United States

^dJet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA, United States

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Mars, atmosphere
Atmospheres, dynamics
Atmospheres, structure

ABSTRACT

Numerical modeling results from the Mars Regional Atmospheric Modeling System are used to interpret the landed meteorological data from the Rover Environmental Monitoring Station onboard the Mars Science Laboratory rover Curiosity. In order to characterize seasonal changes throughout the Martian year, simulations are conducted at Ls 0, 90, 180 and 270. Two additional simulations at Ls 225 and 315 are explored to better understand the unique meteorological setting centered on Ls 270. The synergistic combination of model and observations reveals a complex meteorological environment within the crater. Seasonal planetary circulations, the thermal tide, slope flows along the topographic dichotomy, mesoscale waves, slope flows along the crater slopes and Mt. Sharp, and turbulent motions all interact in nonlinear ways to produce the observed weather. Ls 270 is shown to be an anomalous season when air within and outside the crater is well mixed by strong, flushing northerly flow and large amplitude, breaking mountain waves. At other seasons, the air in the crater is more isolated from the surrounding environment. The potential impact of the partially isolated crater air mass on the dust, water, noncondensable and methane cycles is also considered. In contrast to previous studies, the large amplitude diurnal pressure signal is attributed primarily to necessary hydrostatic adjustments associated with topography of different elevations, with contributions of less than 25% to the diurnal amplitude from the crater circulation itself. The crater circulation is shown to induce a suppressed boundary layer.

1. Introduction

This is the second part of a twopart paper on the meteorology of Gale Crater (5.4S, 137.8E), Mars. In the first part (Pla-Garcia et al., 2016), model simulations conducted with the Mars Regional Atmospheric Modeling System (MRAMS) were compared against observations from the Rover Environmental Monitoring Station (REMS; Gómez-Elvira et al., 2012, 2014) onboard the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) rover Curiosity and were shown to reproduce reasonably well the observed diurnal signals of ground and air temperature, pressure, and winds at Ls 0, 90, 180, and 270. The

reader may refer back to the first part of the paper when references are made to observational and model data comparisons.

Having established the ability of the model to simulate the observed meteorological conditions in Part I, one goal of this second part is to describe the broader meteorological scenarios that are, at the very least, consistent with the observations. A second goal is to elucidate the processes and physics behind the observations. As expected, there are strong indications that there is a complex interplay between circulations over a large range of spatial and temporal scales. In particular, the modeling will demonstrate that global, regional and local circulations must all be considered in order to explain the observational data. These interactions would be difficult, if not impossible, to establish from data alone.

Since there is only a single station with which to validate the model, there is an inherent assumption that the reasonable agreement of the model with the observations (Pla-Garcia et al., 2016) may be extrapolated to all places in the model domain.

* Corresponding author at: 1050 Walnut Street, Suite 300, Boulder, CO 80302, United States. Tel.: +1 720 240 0116.

E-mail address: rafkin.swri@gmail.com, rafkin@boulder.swri.edu (S.C.R. Rafkin).

MRAMS Computational Grids

Fig. 1. MRAMS numerical grids 1–7 (left) and 4–7 (right). The grid spacing on each grid is shown by the alternating black and white bars around the border. The mother domain (grid 1) grid spacing is 240 km and each successive grid decreases in grid spacing by a factor of 3.

Under this assumption, the context provided by the simulations conducted with MRAMS is appropriate and representative of the actual meteorological scenario in which the REMS experiment is embedded.

The domains of the numerical grids are described fully in Part I, but are repeated in Fig. 1, for reference. Seven grids are utilized with the last, highest resolution grid, having grid spacing of 330 m. Likewise, the surface properties, atmospheric initial and boundary conditions, atmospheric dust prescription and general model physics options are also described in Part I.

The observed weather may be considered as the sum of the effects from circulations at a variety of scales (Fig. 2). At the planetary scale, the planetary meridional circulation is driven by the large-scale pressure gradient that feeds off the corresponding meridional thermal gradient. Large-scale stationary and travelling waves are also present. The dominant, zonal wave number two topography of Mars excites standing waves with meridional boundary currents (Joshi et al., 1994). Solar forcing produces the strong, westward migrating diurnal tide that also interacts with the topography to establish higher mode migrating and non-migrating tides, including the eastward moving Kelvin wave (Wilson and Hamilton, 1996; Banfield et al., 2000; Wilson, 2000). So, while there is a steady-state component of the circulation associated with the global latitudinal thermal gradient and planetary waves, there are also planetary scale travelling waves that beat constructively with and destructively against the global mean flow. Going down further to the regional scale, the topographic dichotomy and continental scale topographic variations and impact craters (e.g., Tharsis, Syrtis Major, Hellas, Argyre) exhibit diurnally oscillating upslope and downslope thermal circulations (Rafkin et al., 2002; Michaels et al., 2006; Sta. Maria et al., 2006). Locally, craters, valleys and hills will similarly produce thermally direct circulations that diurnally reverse direction. Finally, at the microscale, there are convective eddies and vortices (including dust devils) that produce high-frequency, but potentially large-magnitude perturbations.

The menagerie of circulations does not generally add linearly. For example, a strong crater circulation can substantially impact the height of the convective boundary layer within the crater, and this can lead to substantial modulation of turbulence and convec-

tive vortices. Likewise, strong regional or planetary scale circulations can substantially disrupt the canonical crater circulation. In the specific case of Gale Crater, substantial non-linear interactions between scales are apparent in the model results and the observations.

There have been many previous modeling studies of atmospheric circulations over the complex terrain on Mars, including craters specifically. Greeley et al., (2003) looked specifically at the effect of blocking by a small crater in relation to downstream aeolian features, and showed that even small, modest topographic barriers can have profound impacts on the flow field. Rafkin et al. (2003) and Toigo and Richardson (2003) modeled a handful of the proposed Mars Exploration Rover (MER) Landing Sites, including Gusev Crater. Gusev Crater is of roughly the same size as Gale Crater, and exhibited strong diurnal upslope and downslope flows in the model solutions. There was also a pronounced suppression of the afternoon boundary layer in the crater due to compensating subsidence from the upslope circulations. Unfortunately, the MERs did not carry any meteorological instrumentation, so a comparison of the model output to observations was not possible. Vasavada et al. (2012) summarized the mesoscale model predictions performed in support of the entry, descent and landing operations for the Mars Science Laboratory at Gale Crater at $\sim L_s 151$. The circulations were largely in agreement with expectations, including pronounced diurnal slope flows on the crater rims and along Mt. Sharp, a suppressed afternoon boundary layer in the crater, and strong and deep afternoon updrafts over the rims and Mt. Sharp. Most recently, Tyler and Barnes (2013; hereafter TB2013), provided a more in depth study of Gale Crater at $L_s 151$.

The work presented in Part I and II of this paper are highly complementary to previous work, especially TB2013. Many of the previously modeled regional and local circulations and phenomena associated with topography and Gale Crater in particular are found in this study. However, as will be shown here, there is considerable seasonal variation, and the interpretation of some phenomena differs in this paper. An alternative to the hypothesis forwarded by TB2013 for the large diurnal pressure signal is offered, and the additional importance of the planetary scale meridional circulation, as well as the transient circulations from the tide, is a novel aspect of this analysis.

Fig. 2. Schematic of dominant circulations that affect the Gale Crater region. The seasonal planetary latitudinal gradient of temperature sets up a large-scale pressure gradient that drives a meridional circulation. Slope circulations are driven by the hemispheric topographic dichotomy and other topographic features, such as Gale Crater. The tide produces a westward travelling wave that sweeps alternating regions of strong convergence and divergence over fixed locations. Turbulent eddies (not shown) will produce rapid variations of seconds to minutes. (Mass stream functions courtesy of J. Hollingsworth; Gale crater topo image credit: ESA/HRC; Mars MOLA topography image credit: NASA/GSFC.)

2. The large-scale circulation

The seasonal shift and sign change of the global, mean meridional circulation has long been established through general circulation modeling (Fig. 2), with results that are consistent with global temperature fields derived from orbit (e.g., Haberle et al., 1993; Forget et al., 1999). A near global, putative Hadley cell has a rising branch in the high latitudes of the summer hemisphere and a subsident branch in the winter hemisphere. The mean surface winds flow from the cold winter hemisphere to the warm summer hemisphere. An upper level return flow is the reverse of the surface flow. Around the equinoxes, there is a brief transition period where the rising branch quickly crosses from one hemisphere into the other as it migrates to its more typical solstitial location. During this transition, there is convergence into the rising branch (similar to the intertropical convergence zone on Earth), and dual Hadley cells with one circulation in each hemisphere. Based on the mean meridional circulation, surface winds at the tropical location of Gale would be expected to reverse seasonally with northerly winds around Ls 270 and southerly winds around Ls 90. At the equinoxes, the winds could go either way as the rising branch transits through the equatorial region.

Looking solely at the mean circulation can be misleading, however. The mean is a mathematical construct that can have little bearing on what is happening at a particular location at a particular time. Mars is known to have a strong, wavenumber two sta-

tionary wave forced by the dominant, wavenumber two topography, and there can be wave flow that is persistently opposed to the mean meridional circulation. These standing waves set up quasi-stationary atmospheric gyres near the surface (Joshi et al., 1997), although the paucity of surface measurements, and wind data in particular, has yet to definitively confirm the existence of such circulations. The tide can also strongly drive surface winds. What really matters is where Gale Crater is within the wave pattern. To establish this global context, general circulation model (GCM) results are the most appropriate data to inspect (e.g., Haberle et al., 1993). By construction, the GCM results lack the influence of the Gale Crater circulation, as the crater is not a resolvable feature.

Fig. 3 displays the average global surface circulation as a function of season, centered at two different Gale Crater local times, roughly corresponding to the very early morning when winds should generally tend to flow downslope, and in the late afternoon when winds should tend to flow upslope. It is immediately clear that the general rule of upslope afternoon winds and downslope night winds is violated at many locations, including Gale Crater. Interrogating the thermal field, it is also clear that the thermal tide circulation is playing a key role in that violation, but so is the overall global thermal circulation. Generally, surface winds tend to flow towards the tidally produced region of maximum air temperature (where pressure is low) and away from regions of cold air temperature (where pressure is high), but if the N-S hemispheric thermal gradient is strong (e.g., at the solstices), the tidal flow is

Fig. 3. 4.5 h averages of the global surface wind circulation as a function of season from the NASA Ames GCM. Rows in descending order are Ls 0, 90, 180, 270. Right column is in the peak of the afternoon. Left column is during the very early morning local time at Gale Crater. Shading indicates near-surface atmospheric temperature in Kelvins. Black lines indicate surface pressure, which can be used as a proxy for large-scale topographic relief (250 Pa increment). The approximate location of Gale Crater (5.45, 137.8E) is shown by a white square.

modulated by a tendency to drive a flow from the cold hemisphere to the warm hemisphere (i.e., the surface branch of the Hadley Cell), regardless of whether it is in opposition to the dichotomy circulation. The tide and mean flow may interact constructively or destructively with the thermally driven upslope and downslope flows. For example, [Rafkin and Michaels \(2003\)](#) noted a dominant effect of the tide in simulations of Valles Marineris, regardless of other slope flow tendencies. In that case, the movement of the low pressure node of the tide along the east-west oriented canyon produced a strong acceleration of the winds toward the tidal low pressure in the afternoon.

During the night at Ls 0, there are downslope winds off Elysium Mons to the north and downslope winds off the cratered highlands to the south. These downslope winds collide in the region of Gale Crater, resulting in a transition region of relative calm. The cold node of the thermal tide, where the surface pressure should be approximately maximum, is roughly coincident with the zone of transition; the tidal flow would tend to counter both downslope flows with a tendency for diverging surface winds directed radially away from the cold, high pressure node. During the day, the winds are upslope toward Elysium Mons and upslope toward the cratered southern highlands. Again, Gale Crater is in the transition zone. The warm node of the thermal tide acts counter to the topographic circulations. The mean global temperature field results in a tendency for surface flow towards the equator. Thus, at Ls 0, it might be expected that the afternoon circulation will be enhanced when both the tide and mean global flow are acting constructively. At night, the mean global flow and tidal divergence act in opposition.

In contrast, at Ls 270, there is on average, overwhelming flow from north to south in the Gale Crater region, regardless of the time of day. In the mean, the southern hemisphere is warm and draws winds from the north as would be expected by the implied large-scale pressure gradient. When the warm node of the tide, where near-surface temperatures are a maximum and pressure should be hydrostatically near minimum, is near the longitude of Gale Crater, the tidal flow will also be from the north. Finally, afternoon heating of the dichotomy will tend to produce upslope flow that will further reinforce northerly winds. Therefore, during the afternoon at Ls 270, the large-scale and regional forcing strongly favors northerly winds. Only the tendency for upslope flow on the southern flank of Elysium Mons tends to drive winds northward, and that local flow is completely overwhelmed. At night, the mean global forcing remains the same, but the cold node of the tide will tend to excite southerly winds. The dichotomy will also tend to force downslope winds. Surprisingly, the flow is still found to be northerly. Apparently, the global meridional circulation is strong enough to counter both the tidal circulation and the forcing from the topographic dichotomy. The nighttime northerly flow appears to be somewhat reinforced by the downslope winds from Elysium Mons. On the large scale, there is very strong north to south flow over the Gale Crater region at all times of day at Ls 270. In addition, the origin of the northerly winds is deep within the northern high latitudes, especially during the afternoon. This would suggest a strong advective corridor is open to transport north polar air towards Gale Crater at Ls 270. As will be shown, the constructive interference of the circulations at Ls 270 makes that a unique time of year at Gale Crater.

3. Regional and crater circulations

3.1. Near-surface circulations

As the scale moves toward smaller scales, the circulations become increasingly complex in both the spatial and temporal do-

main. To gain a true appreciation for the complexity and beauty of the circulations surrounding and within Gale Crater, the reader should proceed no further without first viewing the animations of the circulations provided in the supplementary material. It is simply not possible to fully capture in static figures the myriad of rapidly evolving flows, convergence boundaries, and interacting air masses, all of which are set against the backdrop of the previously described larger-scale circulations and forcings.

Although there is great complexity in the meteorology at the scale of Gale Crater, there are generalizations that may be applied. At all scales, there is a tendency for winds to blow upslope during the day and downslope at night. In the case of Gale Crater, that means winds diverging from the bottom of the crater toward Mt. Sharp and the crater rims during the day, and flowing down the crater rims and Mt. Sharp toward the bottom of the crater where the winds converge ([Fig. 2](#)). The essence of this diurnal dance is evident at all seasons; however the strength of the slope flow varies considerably as a function of season due to non-linear interactions with the larger-scale flows. Additionally, mesoscale dynamical instabilities—most notably large amplitude gravity waves and mountain waves—enter into the mix. These waves are not thermally driven buoyancy circulations, unlike all the previously considered slope circulations. Instead, some mesoscale flows, like mountain waves, are dynamically generated by the interaction of the wind with the topography. These dynamic phenomena can oppose buoyancy forces and provide a mechanism for warm air to descend or cold air to rise. These scenarios are fairly common near mountainous terrain on Earth, and are responsible for downslope wind storms (e.g., Chinook winds in the lee of the Rocky Mountains and Foehn winds in the lee of the Alps ([Beran, 1967](#); [Mathews et al., 1984](#); [Durran, 1986](#); [McGowan, 1997](#); [Hugenholtz, 2013](#))).

By 1100 at all seasons, the local upslope flow around the crater is well established, as can be seen on the mesoscale model grid 5, which fully encompasses Gale Crater ([Fig. 4](#)). At Ls 0 and 90, a convergence boundary rings all but the northernmost crater rim. The boundary is slightly farther south and west at Ls 180, and at Ls 270 the boundary is even farther south. The convergence boundary is associated with the upslope flow on the inner wall of the crater rim meeting with either the upslope on the outer crater rim, or meeting with opposing regional-scale flows. There should be a tendency for a dichotomy upslope, but at Ls 0 the larger-scale circulation—most likely the tide—is producing weak southerly winds that flow down the topographic dichotomy. While it is difficult to unambiguously attribute the tide to the counter-thermal circulation, the phase and location of the tide makes it a prime candidate; the peak amplitude of the tide will traverse the equator and the accompanying afternoon tidal low pressure will tend to dynamically drive winds down the dichotomy toward the low pressure. The result is a very sharp boundary along the southern rim, and a weak to non-existent boundary on the northern rim. The same situation is present at Ls 90, but the larger-scale southerly flow is more pronounced due to both the tidal forcing and the mean meridional pressure gradient. At Ls 180, the southern convergence boundary has pushed further into the highlands than at the earlier seasons, with some evidence that the topographic dichotomy upslope is aiding that greater penetration. Ls 270 is unique in that northerly winds are present throughout the domain at all times of day. The local upslope component on the inner north rim is nearly overwhelmed, and the southern convergence boundary has pushed substantially to the south. The global meridional circulation, the tide and the dichotomy upslope are all reinforcing the northerly winds. Mt. Sharp is under the influence of northerly winds that reinforce the upslope on the north side of the peak. Mt. Sharp also appears to act as an obstacle, causing a slight acceleration of the winds as the atmosphere is deflected

Fig. 4. Near-surface winds (vectors) and potential temperature (shaded) at 1100 LMST as a function of season, as predicted on numerical grid 5. Vectors are plotted at every other grid point. Topography contours are shown in white (500 m spacing). Wind vector scale is shown in the bottom right area of the panels. The location of MSL is shown by the white square.

around the mountain, producing a region of weak and occasionally slightly upslope flow in the southern shadow.

The relative position and strength of the crater convergence boundaries is highly analogous to the interactions of sea breezes with a large-scale mean wind. On Earth, Florida sea breezes provide an ideal example (Burpee, 1979; Arritt, 1993). Sea breezes develop in the morning when the land temperature exceeds the water temperature. In the absence of a mean wind, a convergence boundary is established at each coast where the inward flowing oceanic air meets the air mass over land. Vertical motion is enhanced along the convergence boundary, and it is common for convective clouds to form. Over time, the sea breezes propagate

slowly inland and may even collide over the center of the Florida Peninsula. When a mean wind is added, the system becomes asymmetrical. Where the wind blows in the same direction as the sea breeze propagation, the sea breeze moves rapidly inland. Where the mean wind acts in opposition to the sea breeze, the convergence boundary may remain nearly stationary along the coastline. The convergence boundary at the stationary sea breeze is generally more intense than the propagating sea breeze.

On Mars, the crater circulations are analogous to the Florida sea breeze. When the upslope crater circulation is directed opposite to the mean flow, the convergence boundary will often remain anchored to the topography (or at least will propagate more slowly

than the mean wind would suggest), and a strong updraft results above the convergence boundary. When the mean wind is in the direction of the upslope circulation, the convergence boundary will often surge forward over time in the downstream direction. For example, at Ls 0 and 90, the northern crater convergence boundary is displaced slightly northward and is less well defined than the stronger southern crater convergence boundary anchored to the topography. On the other hand, at Ls 270, the southern boundary is advected southward while the northern boundary remains anchored to the northern crater rim. As will be shown later, the vertical motion is usually strongest at the boundaries that are anchored to the topography. As noted by TB2013, the local crater thermal circulation and the topographic dichotomy circulation are generally not in phase. This can result in quasi-stationary convergence boundaries until the dichotomy circulation matures, at which point one of the boundaries can surge forward in the direction of the dichotomy flow.

At seasons other than Ls 270, the potential temperature is coldest in the floor of the crater. Some cold air is also noticeable in the northern plains, but that air is still somewhat warmer than the air in the crater. The interior crater upslope will tend to produce cold air advection, and this upslope will tend to undercut the warmer air at higher elevations. Of course, the air rising along the crater rim will also tend to heat radiatively, and this will partially (or completely) offset the cold air advection and adiabatic cooling. At Ls 270 there is considerable cold air to the north of the crater. The global scale meridional gradient of temperature coupled with the prevailing northerly winds at this season results in strong cold air advection toward the crater.

By 1600 LMST (Fig. 5), the dichotomy upslope is fully mature and results in northerly winds in the vicinity of the rover at all seasons. The convergence boundary associated with the south crater rim has pushed completely off the domain of grid 5. The northern convergence boundary remains anchored to the north rim, acting in opposition to the regional flow. At Ls 270, cold northerly/northwesterly winds are pouring into the crater. The potential temperature of the air to the northwest of the crater at Ls 270 is actually colder than in the air in the crater, which is unique among the seasons. At other seasons besides Ls 270, the air masses within the crater and outside the crater appear to remain more distinct, as indicated by wind direction shifts and thermal property differences. Topographic passes, such as Peace Valles, do seem to provide a path of least resistance for the exchange of air between the crater and its surroundings, but that exchange appears to be more limited at seasons other than Ls 270.

In the late evening, the crater upslope flow has reversed to downslope at all seasons (Fig. 6). Winds are also flowing down the topographic dichotomy at all seasons except Ls 270 where northerly winds persist, even up the topographic dichotomy. Downslope winds from Mt. Sharp meet the downslope winds from the crater rims to produce a convergence boundary in the interior of the crater. Generally, the air outside the crater is potentially warmer than inside. Any air flowing down the crater rims toward the center of the crater would, from buoyancy considerations, tend to rise up and flow over the colder air at the bottom.

Just prior to sunrise (Fig. 7), the circulation at all seasons, except Ls 270, is very similar. There is a regional southerly flow down the dichotomy, and there is downslope flow from the crater rims and Mt. Sharp toward to the crater bottom. The crater rim flows do not appear to reach to the bottom of the crater. At Ls 270, there is strong flow toward to the crater from the west and from the north, and much of the cold air at the bottom of the crater appears to have been mixed out or replaced by warmer air.

The unique dynamical aspects of Ls 270 can be better appreciated by looking at the output from highest resolution numerical grid (grid 7). Fig. 8 compares near-surface winds and potential

temperature at Ls 270 to those at Ls 90 at three local times. Ls 90 is roughly similar to Ls 0 and 180. At 1600 LMST, there is upslope flow toward the northern crater wall and toward Mt. Sharp at Ls 90. The upslope flow penetrates only to the crater rim where it is met by air flowing up the larger-scale topographic dichotomy. There is a clear and distinct difference in air mass between the crater floor and the region outside the crater. In contrast, at Ls 270, there is an overwhelming northerly flow through the entire grid, and only a very weak indication of any upslope flow on the interior northern crater rim. Evidence for convective cellular structure within the crater at Ls 270 is much more pronounced, which is indicative of more neutral or well-mixed atmospheric structure at this season. The appearance of the cellular structures has been seen previously in other modeling studies (e.g., Rafkin and Michaels 2003) and, based on Earth observations, some mesoscale organization is expected as wind shear increases. (e.g., LeMone et al. 1973; Etling and Brown 1993). In the absence of shear, convection resembles Rayleigh–Bernard convective cells. With increasing shear, thermals organize into linear convective rolls with mesoscale organization. In the very northern region of the grid domain, a narrow band of warm air is present along a convergence boundary.

The dramatic seasonal differences persist into the evening through the early morning. Downslope flow is present at Mt. Sharp and especially at the crater rims at Ls 90. Some air external to the crater flows through Peace Valles and into the crater, but by and large the relatively warmer downslope winds do not penetrate to the crater floor, and the cold air at the very bottom of the crater remains emplaced. In contrast, a strong push of cold air is seen entering the crater from the north at 2200 LMST at Ls 270. This

is not just air flowing through topographic passes like Peace Valles; rather it is a wholesale inundation of the crater from the air to the northwest. Just to the east of this cold inflow of air is an adjacent region of chaotic, warm winds. A strong convergence boundary to the north of the warm region is also present. As will be shown, these features are signatures of a strong breaking mountain wave that mixes warm air aloft down into the crater. The warm band seen at 1600 LMST is a reflection of the development of this wave.

Just prior to sunrise at Ls 270, the air at the bottom of the crater is actually warmer than almost anywhere else in the domain, even though the inflowing air has a lower potential temperature. The air in the crater has lower potential temperature at other seasons. The high potential temperature at Ls 270 originates from air aloft, and further signals the strong vertical mixing associated with the breaking mountain wave. Southerly and easterly winds develop in the vicinity of the rover as the down-rushing air interacts with the ground. Unfortunately, the wind direction data at Ls 270 is sparse during the evening; it is not possible to see the development of this wave in the wind data. However, by late night and early morning, observational wind coverage becomes better. From midnight to sunrise, the modeled wind direction is in excellent agreement with the observations, including the development of southerly and easterly winds (see Part I, Pla-Garcia et al, 2016). The rapid temperature fluctuations observed at night in all seasons is indicative of some mixing and nocturnal turbulence, but the perturbations are strongest at Ls 270. Mt. Sharp does not appear to trigger strong mountain waves, in contrast to the northern crater rims.

The mixing from breaking waves and downslope flows keep the atmosphere warmer than would be expected from pure radiative-convective modeling considerations. With a warmer atmosphere, the temperature gradient between the atmosphere and the cooling ground should increase, and this will drive a larger than expected turbulent heat flux that should tend to reduce the cooling rate of the surface. Fig. 9 shows the turbulent heat flux at 2200 LMST, which confirms expectations. However, the magnitude

Fig. 5. Same as Fig. 4, but at 1600 LMST.

of the fluxes is still generally small, and the thermal mass of the regolith so large, only very small perturbations in the surface temperature might be expected. The model does not show any high frequency variation in the ground temperature. There is variation in the observations, but those variations are all within the error bars of 5 K and may not be statistically significant. Also, the REMS GTS measures a regolith skin temperature that is thinner than the uppermost MRAMS regolith layer, and it should show more variability than the model; GTS will be more sensitive to variations in turbulent heat flux than the 5.0 mm thick top regolith layer in MRAMS.

There is a curious bump in the GTS temperatures between 2000 and 2200 LMST at Ls 270 that does not seem to be present at the

other seasons (see Fig. 4 of Pla-Garcia et al., 2016). This may be a signature of a rapid warming event associated with the onset of breaking mountain waves, but the amplitude of the observed perturbation is smaller than the uncertainty in the measurements. Another possible explanation for the bump in ground temperature change might be related to enhanced turbulence driven by increasingly strong shear at the nocturnal inversion interface. As the nocturnal inversion develops, the winds above become decoupled from the surface and the decrease in friction produces a net acceleration. Once the critical Richardson Number is reached ($Ri \sim <0.25$), shear instabilities can mix warmer air aloft down to the surface. This turbulent mixing process has been observed in the Owens Valley (USA) under similar katabatic wind conditions

Fig. 6. Same as Fig. 4, but for 2200 LMST.

emanating from the Sierra Mountains (Whiteman, 1982; Whiteman and Doran, 1993). Finally, small pressure variations are also noticeable in both the observations (Haberle et al., 2014; Harri et al., 2014) and in the model throughout the night, which are expected in the presence of large amplitude wave activity.

3.2. Downslope winds and mountain waves

Vertical cross-sections provide a clear depiction of slope winds and mountain waves, if they are present. Figs. 10 and 11 show vertical slices from south to north at 2200 LMST and 0400 LMST respectively as a function of season. Neither Ls 90 nor Ls 180 show

any evidence of significant wave activity. Ls 0 shows wave activity on the north rim at 2200, but the bulk of the wave remains above the floor of the crater. By far the strongest wave activity is at Ls 270 at 2200 LMST. Keep in mind that the prevailing wind direction is actually from the north-northwest (see Figs. 6 and 7) so that the cross-section is not capturing the full magnitude of the winds. At both Ls 0 and 270, a northerly wind is found above the crater rim. There is an inversion present near the surface, and the cold near-surface air begins to descend as a katabatic wind aided by an overall mean wind (which must be driven by an overall pressure gradient). Momentarily ignoring the radiative cooling that must be occurring as the air descends, the air will conserve

Fig. 7. Same as Fig. 4, but for 0400 LMST.

potential temperature (i.e., the black potential temperature curves in Fig. 10 become material surfaces). As can be seen at Ls 0 and especially at Ls 270, the potential surfaces descend part way down the northern crater wall, but then rapidly ascend to produce a strong downstream wave pattern. This is a classic mountain wave signature.

Where the potential temperature surfaces become near vertical, the lapse rate is near adiabatic. This neutral buoyancy profile of the atmosphere is susceptible to mixing and overturning. At Ls 270, rotor circulations—gyres in the vertical plane associated with overturning rotating air—develop above and just in front of

the first mountain wave dip. The overturning represents a breaking of the wave, and allows for air several kilometers above to be mixed down to the surface. Where the strong descending branch of the wave meets the surface, warm air aloft is brought directly down to the ground where it mixes with and dilutes the cold air, as seen in Fig. 8.

Strong winds are also associated with mountain waves. One way to understand the strengthening of winds is to once again consider potential temperature surfaces as material surfaces. Along the lee slope, the potential temperature surfaces are packed closely together, creating a Bernoulli effect. Assuming near

Ls 90

Ls 270

Fig. 8. Comparison of near-surface winds and potential temperature at Ls 90 and 270 for three different local times on the highest resolution numerical grid (grid 7). Near-surface winds (vectors) and potential temperature (shaded) with wind vector scale shown in the bottom right area of the panels. Every third model point is plotted for the wind vectors. Topography is shown as white contours (400 m increment). The location of MSL is shown by the white square.

Heat Flux (W/m²) at 2200 Ls 270

Heat Flux (W/m²) at 0400 Ls 270

Fig. 9. Heat flux at 2200 LMST and 0400 LMST at Ls 270 on grid 7. There is an increase in heat flux in the crater where breaking mountain waves bring down warmer air. The location of MSL is shown by the white square.

incompressibility, the air must accelerate through the narrowing material surfaces in order to conserve mass. Thus, strong winds are present along the lee slopes in large amplitude mountain wave situations. The strong winds can be highly localized, and need not extend farther downslope or onto the plains; wind speeds at the surface decrease dramatically where the mountain wave ascends. Importantly, while the air may warm due to mixing, particularly in the near-surface rotor, the wind speeds do not need to be strong, and may be directed in opposition to the downslope flow.

Many nighttime downslope winds that occur on Mars are thought to be of katabatic origin (Savijärvi and Siili, 1993; Fishbaugh and Head, 2002; Sta. Maria et al., 2006; Spiga et al., 2011). Katabatic winds are driven by the gravitational acceleration of negatively buoyant, cold air down a slope. This is not the case for the downsloping wind storms at Gale Crater. While there are elements of katabatic winds in the mountain wave scenario, particularly just after sunset, the mountain wave is dynamically driven and results primarily from the mean wind interacting with the topography. At Ls 270, the northerly winds are particularly strong due to the global meridional circulation. The northerly winds are strengthened by the flow up the topographic dichotomy during the day, and that residual northerly momentum remains strong in the early evening; the dichotomy slope forcing generally lags the crater slope flows [TB2013]. Thus, shortly after sunset and into the early evening, there are strong mean winds that impinge on the northern crater rim. As the cold node of the thermal tide approaches in the early morning hours, it tends to force a southerly wind, which adds to the late arriving dichotomy downslope. Thus, the strong northerly winds start to decrease after midnight, although they never completely reverse.

On Earth, additional conditions beyond strong cross mountain winds must generally be met before a strong mountain wave and associated wind storm will occur. An additional important ingredient is the presence of a mountain top stable layer (Fig. 12) (Klemp and Lilly, 1975; Hoinka, 1985). During the afternoon, the atmosphere of Mars is convective and this condition is not met. How-

ever, a low-level inversion does develop after sunset and into the evening. The development of this stable layer at the crater rim and outside the crater sets up ideal conditions for a mountain wave, which descends to the surface around 2200 LMST. Mountain wave observational data from Earth (Fig. 12) shows a similar descent of a mountain wave with time, and induces strong winds along the lee slope, and rotor circulations further downwind.

As shown in Fig. 12, clouds may form in the upwelling branches of mountain waves on Earth. If the lower levels are moist enough, clouds can signal the rising portion of the low level rotor cloud. At higher levels, clouds can form in the strong mountain wave up-drafts. If rotor or wave clouds do form at Gale Crater, they are most likely to form at night when the mountain wave is strong, temperatures are low, and humidity is relatively high. Unfortunately, there is presently no capability for detecting these clouds at night from the surface or from orbital assets. Very diffuse clouds have been observed during the day (Moore et al., 2015). The modeling results show occasional weak wave activity during the daytime, so afternoon wave clouds are not precluded. The observed clouds also tend to move in different (sometimes opposite) directions to the surface winds, consistent with the wind shear and thermal circulations in the simulations.

In order to try and better bound the season of strong mountain wave activity, two additional MRAMS simulations were conducted for Ls 225 and 315. As with Ls 270, the wave activity was found to start a few hours after sunset peaking within a few hours of 2200 and then weakening slowly until sunrise. The weakening is at least partially due to the tendency for the winds to flow down the topographic dichotomy in opposition to the prevailing northerly winds. Once the sun comes up, the mountain top inversion is destroyed and favorable mountain wave conditions dissipate. Thus, it appears that Gale Crater has a wind storm season that begins somewhere between Ls 180 and 225, extends through Ls 315 and is nearly over by Ls 0. Ls 270 is roughly at the peak of the activity. The evening oscillation found by Harri et al. (2014) may be a surface signature of the development of these strong waves aloft.

Fig. 10. Vertical cross-section (south to north) of wind in the plane of the image (vectors), horizontal wind speed in the plane of the image (shaded) and potential temperature (contours) from grid 6 as a function of season at 2200 LMST. Mt. Sharp is the hill on the left. The north crater rim is the hill on the right. The cross-section corresponds to a slice on grid 5 located just to the west of the peak of Mt. Sharp, $x \approx 120$ km, in Figs. 4–7.

Interestingly, the greatest number of small-scale vortices is found between 1900 and 2200 LMST, particularly between Ls 225 and 270 (Kahanpää et al., in preparation). These cannot be of convective nature, as the atmosphere is not convectively unstable. Instead, the vortices must be signatures of mechanically forced turbulence. Breaking mountain waves and associated gusty winds are the likely source of these vortices, which would form at conver-

gence boundaries. Shear vorticity generated at boundaries can be stretched by vertical motion to produce rotation and associated pressure drops.

During the more quiescent seasons, nighttime slope flows are characterized by more gentle downslope drainage (i.e., katabatic) winds. Most of these flows emanating from the crater rims and Mt. Sharp only occasionally penetrate to the very bottom of the crater,

Fig. 11. Same as Fig. 10, but at 0400 LMST.

and only in localized areas. As the cold air descends, it encounters ever increasing cold air until the point where there is a loss of negative buoyancy. At that point, the descending air glides over the colder air at the bottom of the crater. For example, at Ls 0, 90 and 180, isentropes are nearly horizontal above the crater rim and Mt. Sharp. Concomitantly, the vertical motion is also weak. Winds just above the crater pass, more or less, directly over the crater. Along the interior slopes of the crater walls, the isentropes dip down toward the crater, indicating some downslope drainage flow, which is consistent with the wind field. However, at the very bottom of the crater, the potential temperature is as much as 20 K colder than the descending air. The downslope flow eventually hits that stable layer and rides over the low-level inversion. The boundary between the higher potential temperature downslope winds and the cold air in the crater appears as a convergence boundary in the wind field in Figs. 6 and 7. This scenario is similar to cold air trapping events on Earth (e.g., Zängl, 2005; Wolyn and McKee, 1989).

Rather than envisioning individual parcels of air descending down the slope toward the crater floor, it is more accurate to imagine sheets or slabs of air descending for a short distance

parallel to the slope and then flowing horizontally away from the surface, as shown schematically in Fig. 13. This scenario results in a net downslope flow along the slopes, but it does not generally allow for air at the top of the rim or Mt. Sharp to descend to the very bottom of the crater. The net result is that there is a reduced exchange of air in the bottom of the crater with the air outside the crater.

3.3. Upslope flow, the convective boundary layer and convective vortices

A south–north vertical cross-section through Gale Crater at 1600 LMST is shown in Fig. 14 for each of the modeled seasons. At this time, the convective boundary layer should be fully developed and near its maximum depth. Further, the upslope flow associated with the topographic dichotomy, which takes longer to develop than the local crater upslope, should be mature.

Noting first the potential temperature fields, it is clear that there is a strong capping inversion just above the crater at all seasons. In the northern crater basin, the atmosphere exhibits

Fig. 12. Observational data from a downslope wind storm in the lee of the Rocky Mountains. In the top panel, potential temperature obtained by aircraft is plotted at two different times. Data from the earlier time is above the thick dashed line. Data from the later pass is below the dashed line. The large amplitude mountain wave descends toward the surface over time. In the bottom panel, wind speed is contoured. There is a maximum in wind right near the surface along the slope. The wind decreases quickly away from the mountain range. Figure from Klemp and Lilly (1975).

Fig. 13. Downslope drainage flow forms katabatic sheets. Cold air flows along the surface until it encounters a colder layer of air, at which point it flows horizontally away from the surface and over the colder layer below.

potential temperature that increases with height, representing a somewhat stable rather than convectively neutral thermal profile. The southern basin tends to be slightly more neutral. Vertically oriented isentropes are indicative of convective motion; convection is dominantly found along the rims and above Mt. Sharp. At Ls 270, the southern crater basin is relatively well mixed to altitudes slightly higher than the southern rim and Mt. Sharp. The northern basin is also well mixed and the depth of the convective boundary layer extends well above the northern crater rim.

With the exception of Ls 270, each season shows the expected local upslope pattern, although it is modulated by various other, larger-scale circulations, as previously discussed. Unlike the downslope circulations, the upslope circulations often appear to effectively transport air from the bottom of the crater to the rim. However, this air generally overturns, reverses direction aloft, and then subsides. Undoubtedly, some air gets entrained into the atmosphere outside the crater, but a significant fraction of the air appears to be recycled in the crater.

The daytime upslope circulation has a strong analog to topographic venting circulations in closed or nearly-closed basins on Earth (Wakimoto and McElroy, 1986; Lu and Turco, 1994; McKeendry et al., 1997). Similar circulations are generated on Earth, with winds blowing up slopes, overturning, and producing subsidence over the basin (Kossmann et al., 1998; Serafin and Zardi, 2010). The downward motion acts to suppress the boundary layer, which has the often undesirable effect of also trapping pollutants near the ground. The exception is at the tops of the ridges ringing the basin. Here, plumes of warm air penetrate above the surrounding convective boundary layer and inject polluted air into the free atmosphere above. The rate of injection is not typically enough to completely ventilate the basin. A flushing event of some kind (e.g., a sea breeze or cold front) is necessary to remove the pollutants.

At Ls 0 and 180 (Fig. 14), there appears to be a modest venting event over Mt. Sharp. A deep plume of vertical velocity penetrates 3–4 km into the atmosphere above, and clearly penetrates into the stable layer above. Ls 90 shows a weaker plume slightly on the downwind (southern) side of Mt. Sharp. At Ls 270, the strong prevailing wind appears to have heavily disrupted the crater circulation. Convergence boundaries and plumes at this season have been pushed far to the south if they exist at all. The circulation at Ls 270 is reminiscent of basin flushing events on Earth.

The subsidence in the crater basins and generally shallow convective boundary layer was noted by TB2013, and is identical in nature to that previously noted by Rafkin and Michaels (2003) for other similar features, notably Gusev Crater and Valles Marineris. It is not surprising then, that just like Gusev Crater, the amount of dust devil activity appears to be greatly reduced; subsident motion, shallow convective boundary layers, and weakly stable lapse rates are not conducive to dust devil formation. On the other hand, con-

vection is not completely absent, and while dust devils may not be abundant, at least some level of convective vortex activity should be present. Kahanpää et al. (in preparation) has found dozens of signatures of dustless vortices in the pressure data during the afternoon. Typically, there are one to two transient pressure drops per hour in the early afternoon.

Fig. 15 displays the near surface wind field and potential temperature on grid 6 at 1600 LMST. The purpose of this figure is fourfold. First, it emphasizes that the crater basins are substantially colder (potential temperature) than the slopes, except at Ls 270. This thermal structure will tend to suppress vertical motion. Second, it once again shows how Ls 270 is anomalous. There is little contrast in potential temperature between the crater basins and the ridges or Mt. Sharp; the air is well mixed due to the flushing winds from the north. Third, the divergent near-surface wind field in the northern basin further reflects the general flow toward the slopes, but also demands air sinking from above in order to conserve mass. Finally, the figure shows the mesoscale organization of convective bands that tend to spiral up or around Mt. Sharp at Ls 0 and especially Ls 90. The organization of linear convective updrafts is indicative of convective rolls that are known to form in strong wind situations on Earth (LeMone, 1973; Etling and Brown, 1993; Emanuel, 1994) and have been simulated in Large Eddy Simulations on Mars (e.g., Michaels and Rafkin, 2004). While strongly organized convective bands are not obvious at previous rover locations, this structure is something to look out for as Curiosity makes its way up Mt. Sharp.

34. The crater circulation and pressure

The larger than expected diurnal amplitude of the pressure signal in Gale Crater was identified shortly after meteorological data was returned from REMS. Haberle et al. (2013) and TB2013 attribute the amplification to the local crater circulation. The crater circulation is thought to produce a net export of air during the day as a result of venting upslope flows, and to produce a net import of air at night as a result of inflowing downslope air. For comparison, Viking Lander 2 (VL2) is at nearly the same elevation as Curiosity, but the diurnal pressure amplitude at VL2 is much smaller.

Although the modeling results presented here are largely congruent with those of TB2013, it is not clear that the additional pressure signal amplification can be attributed entirely to crater circulations. At least some of the amplification appears to be a natural and inescapable consequence of the approximate exponential dependence of pressure as function of height. Potential amplification resulting from this dependence was briefly mentioned in Haberle et al. (2013). Additionally, for most seasons, the circulation is far from the concept of an idealized and isolated crater circulation. The addition of regional and large-scale flows and tides superimposed on whatever crater circulation is present means that the canonical view of well-defined crater circulation cells is not always valid. For example, at Ls 270, it is often difficult to find anything close to a canonical crater circulation; the regional and large-scale circulations appear to dominate the local crater circulation signal. Yet, the amplified pressure signal is still present.

The fractional pressure signal amplitude is shown in Fig. 16, and is similar to that in TB2013. Here, fractional pressure is defined as $(p_{\max} - p_{\min})/p_{\text{avg}}$, where each variable is calculated over a diurnal cycle and can be compared directly to Fig. 8 in TB2013. The results here show that the diurnal pressure amplitude is large in Gale crater (and other craters), and is relatively smaller on hills, peaks and ridges. In TB2013, the analysis of the crater circulation effect begins by assuming that pressure is roughly an exponential function of height; a reasonable assumption. Then, any deviation from the average pressure–altitude relationship is assumed to be attributable to the crater circulation effect. This later assumption

Ls 0

Ls 90

Ls 180

Ls 270

Fig. 14. South-north vertical cross-sections at 1600 LMS1. Mount Sharp is the peak in the middle of each panel. Left column: Turbulent kinetic energy (shaded) and potential temperature (contoured). Right column: Wind in the plane of the cross-section (shaded) and wind vectors. The plane of the cross-section is just to the west of Mt. Sharp, at $x \approx 120$ km, in Figs. 4-7.

Fig. 15. Winds (vector) and potential temperature (shaded) on grid 6 at 1600 LMST. Black contours are topography at 400 m increments. The scale for the wind vectors is shown near the bottom right of the plotted data. MSL is located approximately in the center of the figures.

is not entirely justified. While a crater circulation could certainly disrupt the typical pressure–altitude relationship, there could simply be regional differences, or perhaps other non-crater circulations could be exerting an influence.

Examination of Fig. 16 (or TB2013) strongly suggests that the fractional diurnal amplitude is a function of topographic height. The amplitude is generally larger for lower topography, even where

the topography is rather flat and where there is, by definition, no crater circulation contribution. Likewise, the amplitude is smaller where the topography is high. Based on this apparent correlation, it is reasonable to suggest that there is not only a strong correlation between pressure and altitude, but a strong correlation between altitude and diurnal pressure amplitude. If this is the case, then the contribution of the crater circulation (or other

Fig. 16. Diurnal pressure amplitude, $(\rho_{max} - \rho_{min})/\rho_{avg}$, on grid 3 expressed as a percentage for different seasons. Black contours are topography at 500 m intervals.

topographic circulations) to the diurnal signal might be better diagnosed through the deviation of the diurnal amplitude from the average relationship between the diurnal amplitude and altitude.

The relationship between the fractional diurnal pressure amplitude and topographic elevation is shown in Fig. 17. There is a strong and clear relationship between the diurnal pressure amplitude and topographic elevation; the majority of the diurnal pressure amplification is attributable to nothing more than altitude

changes and not due to topographic circulations. Places that are high in altitude tend to have a lower diurnal pressure change regardless of whether they are in a crater or on a ridge. Lower elevations tend to have a higher diurnal amplitude regardless of their proximity to craters.

For a given topographic elevation, there is variation in the associated fractional pressure change, indicating that there is more to the story than just topographic elevation change. Closer inspection

Fig. 17. Fractional diurnal pressure change $(p_{\max} - p_{\min})/p_{\text{avg}}$ as a function of topographic elevation for four different seasons and specifically for the Gale Crater area at Ls 0. Note that Gale data forms a well-defined line. Other topographic features produce the other linear data patterns (some of which have been marked with dashed lines for illustrative purposes). The data are taken from the same area (grid 3), as displayed in Fig. 16.

shows that within the cluster of points in Fig. 17, there are loci of points that tend to form discrete lines. Each of these lines is associated with a major topographic feature. As an example, data taken from the Gale Crater region group into a tightly focused line, as shown by the asterisks. Other features produce linearly related

data that together produce the overall cluster of points in Fig. 17. There are some altitudes for which the pressure variation is larger compared to Gale Crater, and some places where it is smaller. Gale Crater itself is unexceptional and tends to fall roughly in the middle

of the data for a given elevation. The conclusion from this is that the pressure deviations in Gale Crater do not deviate substantially from what would be expected due solely to elevation changes. There are some locations outside of Gale Crater where the diurnal signal is amplified, and some places where it is diminished compared to the overall mean. Even so, the variation of the diurnal pressure change at a given surface elevation is typically no more than about 25% of the total, regardless of whether the location is in a crater, on a hill, or on a plain. In other words, about 75% of the amplification is explainable solely by elevation change, while the topographic circulations can account for the $\sim 25\%$ residual, and that residual may be in either direction. The underlying reason for this can be understood through the following analysis.

Consider the simple scenario shown in Fig. 18. Point A is located at a lower elevation than Point B. For simplicity, assume that the atmosphere is isothermal. This assumption will be relaxed shortly to a more general situation. Starting at some height z^* far above

the atmosphere, it is assumed that the pressure surface is horizontal.

$$\frac{\partial \ln p}{\partial z} = -\frac{g}{RT} \quad (1)$$

Since the atmosphere is isothermal, the integrand on the right

side of Eq. (1) is constant and the integral may be easily evaluated. However, the mean value theorem can be used to provide a more general expression for an arbitrary temperature profile:

Fig. 18. Schematic of idealized scenario with two atmospheric columns at location A and B. Location A is at lower elevation than B. At some altitude z^* , the pressure at location A and B are assumed to be the same.

where $\overline{(\frac{1}{T})}$ is the mean inverse temperature from z^* down to the surface. For an isothermal atmosphere, the mean inverse temperature is simply the reciprocal of the atmospheric temperature. A functional expression for $T(z)$ would need to be specified to find the inverse mean for the more general case.

For now, the assumption of an isothermal atmosphere is reinstated. During the afternoon, the mean temperature (T_{hot}) is assumed to be higher than at night (T_{cold}). The ratio of the surface pressures between the afternoon and evening is then

$$\frac{p_{\text{hot}}}{p_{\text{cold}}} = \frac{e^{-\overline{(\frac{1}{T_{\text{hot}}})} (z^* - z_{\text{sfc}})}}{e^{-\overline{(\frac{1}{T_{\text{cold}}})} (z^* - z_{\text{sfc}})}} = e^{\overline{(\frac{1}{T_{\text{hot}}})} - \overline{(\frac{1}{T_{\text{cold}}})} (z^* - z_{\text{sfc}})} \quad (4)$$

where $\frac{1}{T} = \overline{(\frac{1}{T})}$. Eq. (4) shows that the amplitude of the diurnal signal is a function of the change in the column temperatures and a function of the height from the reference pressure level to the surface. For the same change in temperature between day and night, a station at a lower elevation will record a larger diurnal pressure signal. Further, it is an exponential increase. This result is purely a result of day to night variations in temperature and no topographic circulations have been included.

Let h be the distance between z^* and the surface at location B, and let D be the elevation drop from B to A, as shown in Fig. 18. Then, the fractional change in pressure between point A and B, from Eq. (4) is

$$\frac{p_{\text{hot, A}}}{p_{\text{cold, A}}} = \frac{e^{-\overline{(\frac{1}{T_{\text{hot}}})} (z^* - h - D)}}{e^{-\overline{(\frac{1}{T_{\text{cold}}})} (z^* - h - D)}} = e^{\overline{(\frac{1}{T_{\text{hot}}})} - \overline{(\frac{1}{T_{\text{cold}}})} D} \quad (5)$$

$$\ln p = \frac{1}{R} \int_{z^*}^z \frac{g}{T} dz + \ln p_{z^*} \quad (2)$$

ponential function of the elevation difference. Fig. 17 shows a similar exponential dependence. For example, the data for Gale Crater is decidedly non-linear and closer to an exponential-like relationship.

The result in Eq. (5) is consistent with Figs. 16 and 17, and strongly suggests that the bulk of the increased amplitude could be due to nothing more than relative changes in elevation. For example, for $g = 3.72 \text{ m s}^{-2}$, $R = 192 \text{ J/kg}$, $D = 3000 \text{ m}$, $1/H_{\text{cold}} = 200 \text{ K}^{-1}$, the fractional pressure change at A would be

$$= 210 \text{ K}^{-1},$$

According to Eq. (5), the pressure amplitude at the lower eleva-

tion point A will be larger than point B by a factor that is an expo-

$$p_{sfC} = p_* e^{\frac{g}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} \right) (z_A - z_{sfC})}, \quad (3)$$

$\sim 2x$ that at B. Again, this amplification is produced completely in the absence of a crater circulation. Instead, the amplification is a result of a hydrostatic adjustment associated with the normal heating and cooling of the atmosphere; it is a diurnal hydrostatic effect. It is the deviations from this hydrostatic amplification that are associated with topographic (or other) circulations.

The lower diurnal amplitude at VL2, despite its similar elevation to Curiosity, is explained by the inherent variation of tidal amplitude as a function of latitude, and to a lesser degree, longitude. VL2 is in the middle latitudes where solar heating is less than in the tropics. However, within the VL2 region, the theory presented above predicts that lower elevations would experience a higher diurnal pressure amplitude, regardless of whether such locations are in a crater.

Clearly, for surface pressure to change from day to night, there must be a circulation that changes the mass of the atmosphere above. It is primarily the thermal tide that accomplishes this movement of atmospheric mass. The tide is a strong convergent/divergent, nearly hydrostatic circulation. The pressure wave typically associated with the tide is precisely coupled to the thermal properties and net divergence in the atmospheric column. Deviations from the expected surface pressure variations from day to night, which are exponentially dependent on the surface elevation, can be attributed to circulations (like crater circulations) other than the tide.

An argument can be made that the derivation of Eq. (5) is oversimplified due to an assumed isothermal atmosphere. However, it can be shown that any reasonable assumption of $T(z)$ leads to the same basic result. The general solution is beyond the scope of this paper, and is instead the topic of another paper in preparation. It is noted that the middle expression in Eq. (5) is in fact, a general solution, if the scale height for the column in A is assumed to be different than B. If the mean inverse scales heights between day and night do not differ substantially between A and B, then the dominant variable becomes D.

Observations, and especially the modeling results here, suggest that the circulation in Gale crater is far from the ideal, isolated upslope and downslope circulation. The actual circulation is highly asymmetric, and the convergence boundaries are often pushed far away from the crater, into the crater, or can be anchored to the topography. In most cases, there is prevailing wind that blows through and over the crater. If this wind were constant, there would be no net convergence or divergence contribution, but that is not the case. Even in the absence of the thermal upslope and downslope crater circulations, the mean wind interacts with the topography in complex ways to produce regions of net convergence and divergence that are superimposed on whatever local circulation may be present.

While the crater circulation may perturb the diurnal pressure signal from what might be expected, it is also likely that the crater circulation and the interaction of that circulation with the topographic dichotomy circulation, the tide, and the overall mean flow are responsible for the high frequency perturbations in the observed and modeled diurnal pressure signal. The diurnal pressure signal at Ls 270 is comparatively smooth compared to the other seasons. At the same time, it does exhibit the larger-than-expected diurnal amplitude. The current analysis indicates that the diurnal amplitude is the result of the day to night temperature variation and the lower elevation of the crater floor and not primarily due to the crater circulation itself. The lack of structure much beyond wave number 1 at Ls 270 indicates that circulations at scales smaller than the tide contribute very little to the pressure cycle. This is consistent with the strong prevailing wind flushing the crater, and the quashing of a well-defined crater circulation. However, even with a very weak, nearly disrupted crater circulation, the diurnal amplitude at Ls 270 remains large.

At Ls 0, 90 and 180 the crater circulation and the regional dichotomy circulation are better defined than at Ls 270. The result of the better organized and localized circulation is the presence of higher frequency structures in the pressure signal. Hydrostatically, increases in pressure are indicative of a cooling of the atmospheric column; the opposite is true for decreases in pressure. If the high frequency perturbations are assumed to be associated with changes in temperature of the lower atmosphere, then to first order, the changes in pressure are due to air masses of slightly different temperatures moving through the rover location. From hydrostatic scaling arguments (i.e., Eq. (1)), changes of only a few Kelvin can produce noticeable temperature variations. Such small thermal variations are not readily visible in the observations, and are generally below the retrieval error bars. It may be possible that statistical analysis can pull out a signal that relates the small temperature variations to pressure changes. Additionally, shifts in wind direction or wind speed might be expected as air mass boundaries propagate over the rover. Unfortunately, the observational wind record is even less conducive to identification of these changes.

4. Implications for dust and sand, water, noncondensables, methane and other trace gases

The diurnally and seasonally variable circulations and thermal structures have potential implications for the local and global cycles of dust and sand, water, putative but ephemeral methane, noncondensables, and other trace gases. Each of these cycles is considered below.

4.1. The dust and sand cycle

The fate of dust and sand in Gale Crater is of interest for several reasons. First, one hypothesis for the formation of Mt. Sharp is that it is of aeolian origin (Kite et al., 2013). If Mt. Sharp formed under similar wind conditions to those at present, then that would suggest that the upper levels of Mt. Sharp should currently be a net sink for either sand or especially dust (or both). On the other hand, if Mt. Sharp is of aeolian origin, but was formed during different conditions, such as might be forced by obliquity changes, then current aeolian processes could be eroding the peak. The erosive materials could then either be carried out of the crater or could be deposited at lower elevations.

The second reason that dust and sand transport is of interest is because of the wide diversity of aeolian features in Gale Crater, as well as the very specific geographical distribution of aeolian features. For example, the dark sand dunes are a striking feature that ring Mt. Sharp (Fig. 19). However, the dunes are distributed asymmetrically. Imagery clearly shows that the northern lowlands around Mt. Sharp have very few dark dunes, whereas the eastern and western dunes are more extensive. Dark material covers the southern portion of the crater and extends onto the southern crater highlands in what could be characterized as a very large dark crater wind streak (Thomas et al., 1981; Veverka et al., 1981; Thomas et al., 1984).

Based on the model results, dust and sand should be mobilized most easily and frequently at the season centered around Ls 270. Strong northerly to northwesterly winds persist at this season and are reinforced by mountain wave activity from late evening through early morning. The maximum surface stress at Ls 270 is also shown in Fig. 19. The stress at other seasons is substantially less than at Ls 270. The largest stress is on the northwest interior rim of the crater and is associated with the strong downslope winds and mountain wave activity. Within the crater, the stress is rather small and probably below the lifting threshold of dust, and perhaps even the saltation threshold. Of course, locally larger

Fig. 19. Gale Crater exhibits a wide variety of aeolian features. The dark sand dunes and dark material stretching into the crater highlands to the south are visible from orbit (left). Image Credit: JPL/NASA-Caltech. On the right, the maximum wind stress from grid 5 at Ls 270 is shown.

stresses at scales below that which can be captured on the displayed grid (grid 5) may exist.

There is no obvious correlation between the maximum stress and the dark dune material either inside or downstream of the crater. This suggests that the origin and maintenance of these dunes is perhaps more complex than simply considering the wind stress during the most windy season.

The stress around and on top of Mt. Sharp is also generally small. Thus, widespread dust lifting or aeolian activity is not favored at Ls 270 or at any other season when the stresses are even smaller. If Mt. Sharp is undergoing aeolian erosion, the model results suggest it is extremely slow. What is not clear is where any material lifted from Mt. Sharp might go. Any dust that is mobilized and entrained into the atmosphere could be carried out of the crater. As shown in the cross-sections, winds tend to blow over the crater rather than into the crater. Furthermore, if dust is lifted and then lofted, it can more easily be carried downwind out of the crater. Mt. Sharp and the crater rims are susceptible to strong afternoon updrafts and plumes that could inject dust at least several kilometers above the rim. Horizontal advection could then carry the dust outside the crater faster than it could sediment. On the other hand, if dust is lifted during the night, some of the material might tend to flow down into the crater basin.

Based on retrievals of vertical dust profiles from MSL Navigation Camera images, [Moore et al. \(2016\)](#) found that the dust loading above the crater rim was greater than in the crater. This is generally consistent with the findings that dust lifting is generally weak within the crater, and that dust lifted outside the crater will tend to blow over the crater, thereby creating a dust inversion. The exception was around Ls 270, where the dust abundance in the crater was found to be similar to the dust above the crater. Again, this is consistent with the strong mixing and flushing of the crater air mass found in the model.

Without an active dust cycle in the model, the fate of sand and dust at different times of day at different seasons is difficult to determine. MRAMS does have the capability to simulate a fully active dust cycle including dust lifting, sedimentation, and the radiative forcing from the lifted dust. The detailed investigation of the dust

and sand cycle with those additional physical parameterizations is left for future work.

4.2 The water cycle

The primary source of water vapor to the atmosphere is the northern polar cap during the Spring and early Summer. Once the winter CO₂ retreats, the underlying polar water ice is exposed and begins to sublimate. The water is transported equatorward where it is manifested in the tropical aphelion cloud belt. If transport is assumed to be the result of the Hadley Cell, then the polar water is carried aloft in the northern high latitude rising branch before moving equatorward and eventually toward the southern high latitudes. If this is the case, then the equatorial surface regions are moistened only once the water has moved to the southern hemisphere, descended to the surface, and is then moved northward at the surface back toward the equator. At the same time, it is likely that transient waves (e.g., storm systems) as well as boundary currents associated with planetary-scale stationary waves also advect and mix water equatorward.

In the specific case of Gale Crater, the source air mass region during the Spring and early Summer can be gleaned by looking at the large-scale scale flow (i.e., [Fig. 3](#)). Based on the surface winds predicted by the GCM, there is no obvious strong transport corridor from the northern polar water source region to Gale Crater. The flow is either dominantly east–west, or more typically, has a southerly component. Therefore, the source air mass region for air in Gale Crater during the northern spring and summer is from the southern highlands, which are relatively dry according to water column abundances retrieved from the Thermal Emission Spectrometer ([Smith, 2002](#)). Nevertheless, the air and ground temperatures tend to be coldest around Ls 90, which could drive the relative humidity to near saturation values even for low absolute water content.

Only at Ls 270 is there model evidence for a direct transport connection to the northern polar regions. However, this is the season when the north pole is a water trap. Thus, the air coming from the poles should be no moister than the saturation vapor pressure

at the temperature of polar ice cap (~145 K). By the time this air makes its way to Gale Crater, it has warmed substantially. Night-time air and surface temperatures drop only to ~200 K. Relative humidity should be correspondingly low.

MRAMS results suggest that the air mass at the very bottom of the crater does not readily mix with air from the air outside the crater, except for the period around Ls 270. Gale Crater might be considered more like a leaky bowl. Some air is exchanged at night in localized areas and for short periods of time when downsloping air finds its way through topographic gaps. There is also some mixing at the top of the nocturnal inversion, and almost certainly some venting of air up the crater rims and Mt. Sharp during the day. Around Ls 270, the mixing and exchange of the crater air mass with the air outside the crater appears nearly complete.

The net result of a “leaky” crater is that the water abundance (and other relatively long-lived chemical species) should lag the abundance outside the crater. The amount of lag depends on the mixing rate. If the air in the crater is sufficiently isolated, there may be noticeable seasonal effects. For example, assume that the crater air mass and exterior air have the same properties around Ls 270 when the crater is effectively flushed. As the equinox approaches, the circulation and stability in the crater change such that the crater air mass becomes increasingly isolated. Then, as the air outside the crater changes, the crater will only reflect those changes according to a mixing time scale. If the air outside the crater begins to moisten, the crater will moisten only at the rate allowed by the limited mixing. As the air outside the crater begins to dry, the crater will stay moist for a little while longer until the drier air begins to mix in.

Like dust, MRAMS was not run with an active water cycle although it has that capability. Future simulations with an active water cycle will help to better quantify the fate of water. The relative humidity observations, which have been largely ignored in this study, will play a crucial role in that future work.

4.3. Noncondensables

The previous discussion on water is directly relevant to noncondensables. Like water, the enrichment of noncondensables (primarily N₂ and Ar) is controlled by polar cap processes. The fraction of noncondensables peaks over the winter pole when the CO₂ ice cap is at a maximum (Sprague et al., 2004, 2007; Nelli et al., 2007).

If complete mixing is assumed at Ls 270, and if there is an efficient transport corridor from the northern polar cap, then the noncondensable abundance in Gale Crater should be reflective of the high enriched values at the pole. As the year progresses and Gale Crater becomes more isolated, it will retain the high enrichment value longer than the air outside the crater. Over time, it will tend to relax toward the values outside the crater, but only on a timescale governed by the rate of mixing. During the southern winter, the enrichment process switches to the southern pole. This is exactly when the winds tend to come from the south at Gale Crater. Thus, the air in Gale Crater will tend to relax toward this elevated value. The net result is that Gale Crater may have a mean annual enrichment value that is above the value outside the crater. This entire argument depends, however, on there being some large-scale seasonal variation of non-condensables at the location of Gale Crater; if the enriched air is mixed out prior to arrival in the Gale Crater region then this possible test of crater mixing would not be applicable. Further, if the mixing time scale is short, despite the inferred low mixing rate, this effect may not be detectable.

Noncondensable measurements by the SAM instrument might be the best way to test the Gale Crater mixing hypothesis. If the noncondensable value lags the values in the tropics retrieved from orbit, this could be indicative of a partially isolated crater air mass.

Furthermore, it may be possible to estimate the mixing timescale. An elevated mean annual noncondensable enrichment would also be an indicator that mixing between the crater and its environment is limited.

4.4. Methane and other trace gases

The putative in situ detection of methane by SAM has garnered significant attention because of the potential implications for the presence of indigenous Martian organisms (Webster et al., 2013, 2015). In the absence of a yet-to-be-confirmed rapid destruction mechanism, the photochemical lifetime of methane is of order 100 years. This is much longer than the atmospheric mixing time scale, and thus the gas should tend to be well mixed except when near a source or shortly after an episodic release. The observed spike of 7 ppb from the background of <1 ppb, and then the rapid return to the background level is, therefore, curious. The rise in concentration was reported to start around sol 300 (~Ls 325), peaked shortly after sol 500 (~Ls 70), and then dropped to background values prior to sol 600 (~Ls 116).

Two scenarios are considered in the context of the circulations predicted by MRAMS. The first scenario is the release of methane from somewhere outside the crater. The second is a release of methane within the crater. In both cases, the release is assumed to take place near the season when the rise of concentration was first noted (~Ls 325). This is a transitional time at Gale Crater, when the flushing winds are giving way to the more limited mixing crater scenario.

In the situation where the release was outside the crater, mixing should be sufficient to bring the crater methane abundance to something close to the larger-scale environmental value. As the crater becomes more isolated with time, the methane abundance will begin to lag whatever the value is outside the crater. If the release was far from the crater, the external ~7 ppb value might be expected to slowly decrease as the methane becomes increasingly well-mixed on a global scale, and as some of that air mixes slowly into the crater. Notably, it is unlikely that the global value would relax all the way back to the initial background value unless the mixing is deep into the atmosphere. This is not entirely out of the realm of possibility given the very high altitude dust layers recently observed (McCleese et al., 2010; Heavens et al., 2015) and the potential for deep vertical transport (Rafkin et al., 2002; Rafkin, 2012).

For the elevated methane levels in the crater to drop rapidly back to background levels, at least two things would need to happen. First, the external crater environment would have to drop at least as rapidly to the background levels. This seems possible only if there is very deep mixing that spreads the release through a very large volume of atmosphere, or if a rapid destruction mechanism is invoked. The second thing that would have to happen is that the crater air would have to mix nearly completely with the external crater air. The model results at Ls 90, which bounds the period between the observed peak and the return to the background levels, is not fully supportive of this idea. However, while mixing seems limited, it may still be possible that the mixing time scale is sufficient to affect the necessary change. More work is needed to establish the amount of mixing.

In the second scenario, the release is assumed to be within the crater. In this case, some mixing of this air with external crater air at background values can be assumed. Depending on the rate of mixing, it is possible that the value could decay to the background levels in the given time. Thus, from a mixing standpoint, the second scenario seems at least plausible. However, this scenario also requires a form of special pleading. There is nothing exceptionally special about Gale Crater. It is hard to argue that if methane is being released on Mars, that Gale Crater is the sole source. Rather,

if it is coming out at Gale Crater, it is likely to be coming out in many other places on Mars. If that is the case, then the background values should likely be far higher than the observed values.

Mischna et al. (2011) modeled a localized release of methane on Mars with a GCM and concluded that a best match to observations would be found if a release occurred just prior to observations (before it could be substantially diluted) and if the release was instantaneous rather than gradual. Furthermore, a point source release was less consistent with observations than a broad, regional release. Because the study was done with a GCM, the influence of localized topography, such as Gale Crater, was not included. Whether other trace gases exhibit peculiar behaviors has yet to be determined. To the extent that SAM and perhaps other MSL instrumentation can measure trace gases, particularly those whose presence are less controversial than methane, the seasonal and diurnal variability and abundance could provide further clues about the mixing time scale of the crater. Oxygen species (O, O₂ and/or O₃) are potential candidates for investigation, as is CO.

5. Summary

In this second part of a two-part paper, numerical modeling results conducted with MRAMS were presented in order to provide some context for the REMS observations discussed in the first part paper, and to elucidate the processes underlying the REMS observations. As expected, based on previous modeling, Gale Crater has a complex meteorological environment—more so than any other site visited with a suite of landed meteorological instrumentation.

At any given time, the local conditions are a result of a variety of scales of motion ranging from seasonal planetary-scale circulations, the thermal tide, slope flows along the topographic dichotomy, slope flows along the crater slopes and Mt. Sharp, large amplitude mountain waves, and turbulent motions. The importance of some of these circulations in determining the overall wind environment, particularly the thermal tide and mountain waves, has previously been given very little attention.

In order to characterize seasonal changes throughout the Martian year, simulations were conducted at Ls 0, 90, 180 and 270. Two additional simulations at Ls 225 and 315 were explored to better understand the unique meteorological setting centered around Ls 270. Ls 270 was shown to be an anomalous season when air within and outside the crater was well mixed by strong, flushing, northerly flow and large amplitude breaking mountain waves. At other seasons, the air in the crater was more isolated from the surrounding environment. The amount of isolation and the rate of mixing require further study.

The potential impact of a partially isolated crater air mass on the dust, water, noncondensable and methane cycles was considered. There was no obvious association of aeolian features, particularly the dark sand dunes ringing Mt. Sharp, to the periods of greatest wind stress. This suggests the formation of these dunes may be more complex than a simple correlation with the strongest wind speeds and direction. The vertical profile of dust inferred through Navigation Camera images is consistent with the wind and thermal structure from the model; the stable layers in the crater inhibit the dusty external air from flowing into the crater, and the wind speeds do not indicate widespread periods of dust lifting in the crater. Dust devils are uncommon. Therefore, the air in the crater tends to have a lower dust loading than the air above. Ls 270 was an exception when the crater air (and dust) should be well mixed with the air external to the crater.

Water vapor and noncondensables are related to polar processes and their abundance at Gale Crater depends on hemispheric transport and mixing of that air into the crater. If the air in the crater is partially isolated for most of the year, the abundance of all tracer species, including methane and other long-lived trace

gases, should lag the trends external to the crater. For water, Gale Crater should be dry year round (in absolute terms), but may show anomalously high concentrations of noncondensables compared to the surroundings. The variation of the crater circulation with season makes it unlikely that the putative methane detection could have a source region outside the crater. However, a source region inside the crater is problematic due to special pleading arguments.

In contrast to previous studies, the large diurnal pressure signal was attributed primarily to changes in surface elevation rather than to the crater circulation. An increase in the amplitude of the diurnal signal is a necessary consequence of hydrostatic changes associated with the heating and cooling of a column of air from day to night. The Gale Crater circulation may account for only ~25% of the amplified diurnal pressure signal.

The boundary layer in the crater tends to be suppressed due to compensating subsidence generated in response to upwelling afternoon slope flows. This is similar to previous studies such as Gusev Crater and Valles Marineris. The suppressed boundary layer suppresses convective mixing and dust devil formation. The suppressed daytime boundary layer and isolated crater air mass overall is analogous in many ways to closed basins on Earth. Updraft plumes along the topographic boundaries of the basin can partially ventilate the basin, but are unable to fully do so. Nevertheless, the plumes can penetrate well above the surrounding mixed layer and can inject dust and other constituents into the free atmosphere above.

Acknowledgements

As with all large space missions, the ability to conduct science depends upon the dedication of hundreds of scientists, engineers and managers. The authors are grateful for the hard work of the MSL team, without whose dedication none of this work could be accomplished. The authors would also like to explicitly thank the REMS science team for their efforts. Additionally, this manuscript benefited greatly from comments and discussions provided by Isaias Carrasco, Henrik Kahanpää, Germán Martínez, Bob Haberle, Claire Newman, Javier Martin-Torres, Eduardo Sebastian, Alejandro Soto, Patricia Valentin-Serrano, and Mari-Paz Zorzano. Two anonymous reviewers provided detailed comments that significantly improved the manuscript and their efforts are greatly appreciated. This work was supported by the NASA/Jet Propulsion Laboratory under subcontract 1509303 and by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness under contracts AYA2011-25720 and AYA2012-38707. Part of this research was carried out at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, under a contract with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.icarus.2016.01.031](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2016.01.031).

References

- Arritt, R.W., 1993. Effects of the large-scale flow on characteristic features of the sea breeze. *J. Appl. Meteorol.* 32 (1), 116–125.
- Banfield, D., Conrath, B., Pearl, J.C., et al., 2000. Thermal tides and stationary waves on Mars as revealed by Mars Global Surveyor thermal emission spectrometer. *J. Geophys. Res.* 105 (E4), 9521–9537.
- Beran, D.W., 1967. Large amplitude lee waves and chinook winds. *J. Appl. Meteorol.* 6 (5), 865–877.
- Burpee, R.W., 1979. Peninsula-scale convergence in the south Florida sea breeze. *Mon. Weather Rev.* 107 (7), 852–860.
- Durrán, D.R., 1986. *Mountain Waves. Mesoscale Meteorology and Forecasting.* Springer, pp. 472–492.
- Emanuel, K.A., 1994. *Atmospheric Convection.* Oxford University Press.
- Etling, D., Brown, R., 1993. Roll vortices in the planetary boundary layer: A review. *Boundary Layer Meteorol.* 65 (3), 215–248.

- Fishbaugh, K.E., Head, J.W., 2002. Chasma Boreale, Mars: topographic characterization from Mars Orbiter Laser Altimeter data and implications for mechanisms of formation. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets* 107 (E3), 2-1-2-26.
- Forget, F., Hourdin, F., Fournier, R., et al., 1999. Improved general circulation models of the Martian atmosphere from the surface to above 80 km. *J. Geophys. Res.* 104 (24), 155-176.
- Gómez-Elvira, J., Armiens, C., Castañer, L., et al., 2012. REMS: The environmental sensor suite for the Mars Science Laboratory rover. *Space Sci. Rev.* 170, 583-640. doi:10.1007/s11214-012-9921-1.
- Gómez-Elvira, J., Armiens, C., Carrasco, I., et al., 2014. Curiosity's Rover environmental monitoring station: overview of the first 100 sols. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets* 119 (7), 1680-1688. doi:10.1002/2013JE004576.
- Greeley, R., Kuzmin, R.O., Rafkin, S.C., et al., 2003. "Wind-related features in Gusev crater, Mars. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets* 108 E12.
- Haberle, R.M., Pollack, J.B., Barnes, J.R., et al., 1993. Mars atmospheric dynamics as simulated by the NASA Ames general circulation model. 1. The zonal-mean circulation. *J. Geophys. Res.* 98 (E2), 3093-3123.
- Haberle, R.M., Gómez-Elvira, J., de la Torre Juárez, M., et al., 2014. Preliminary interpretation of the REMS pressure data from the first 100 sols of the MSL mission. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets* 119 (3) 2013JE004488.
- Harri, A.M., Genzer, M., Kempainen, O., et al., 2014. Pressure observations by the Curiosity rover: Initial results. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets* 119 (1), 82-92.
- Heavens, N.G., Cantor, B.A., Hayne, P.O., et al., 2015. Extreme detached dust layers near Martian volcanoes: Evidence for dust transport by mesoscale circulations forced by high topography. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 42, 3730-3738. doi:10.1002/2015GL064004.
- Hoinka, K.P., 1985. Observation of the airflow over the Alps during a Föhn event. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* 111 (467), 199-224.
- Hughenoltz, C.H., 2013. Anatomy of the November 2011 windstorms in southern Alberta, Canada. *Weather* 68 (11), 295-299.
- Joshi, M.M., Haberle, R.M., Schaeffer, J., et al., 1997. Seasonal variations in low level flow in the NASA-Ames Mars GCM. *Adv. Space Res.* 19 (8), 1261-1265.
- Joshi, M.M., Lewis, S.R., Read, P.L., et al., 1994. Western boundary currents in the atmosphere of Mars. *Nature* 367 (6463), 548-552.
- Kahanpää, H., Newman, C., Moores, J., et al. (2015). "Convective vortices and dust devils at the MSL landing site: annual variability." in preparation.
- Kite, E.S., Lewis, K.W., Lamb, M.P., et al., 2013. Growth and form of the mound in Gale Crater, Mars: Slope wind enhanced erosion and transport. *Geology* 41 (5), 543-546.
- Klemp, J., Lilly, D., 1975. The dynamics of wave-induced downslope winds. *J. Atmospheric Sci.* 32 (2), 320-339.
- Kossmann, M., Vögtlin, R., Corsmeier, U., et al., 1998. Aspects of the convective boundary layer structure over complex terrain. *Atmos. Environ.* 32 (7), 1323-1348.
- LeMone, M.A., 1973. The structure and dynamics of horizontal roll vortices in the planetary boundary layer. *J. Atmospheric Sci.* 30 (6), 1077-1091.
- Lu, R., Turco, R.P., 1994. Air pollutant transport in a coastal environment. Part I: Two-dimensional simulations of sea-breeze and mountain effects. *J. Atmospheric Sci.* 51 (15), 2285-2308.
- Mathews, T., Lester, P., Hicks, R., 1984. Sodar observations of chinooks and arctic front passages across the Eastern slopes of the Canadian Rockies. *Atmos. Ocean* 22 (3), 328-342.
- McCleese, D.J., Heavens, N.G., Schofield, J.T., et al., 2010. The structure and dynamics of the martian lower and middle atmosphere as observed by the Mars Climate Sounder: 1. Seasonal variations in zonal mean temperature, dust and water ice aerosols. *J. Geophys. Res.* 115, E12016. doi:10.10129/2010JE003677.
- McGowan, H.A., 1997. Meteorological controls on wind erosion during Föhn wind events in the eastern Southern Alps, New Zealand. *Can. J. Earth Sci.* 34 (11), 1477-1485.
- McKendry, I., Steyn, D., Lundgren, J., et al., 1997. Elevated ozone layers and vertical down-mixing over the Lower Fraser Valley, BC. *Atmos. Environ.* 31 (14), 2135-2146.
- Michaels, T.I., Colaprete, A., Rafkin, S.C.R., 2006. Significant vertical water transport by mountain-induced circulations on Mars. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 33 (16), 5.
- Michaels, T.I., Rafkin, S.C.R., 2004. Large-eddy simulation of atmospheric convection on Mars. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* 130 (599), 1251-1274.
- Mischna, M.A., Allen, M., Richardson, M. I., Newman, C.E., Toigo, A.D., 2011. Atmospheric modeling of Mars methane surface releases. *Planet. Space Sci.* 59 (2), 227-237.
- Moores, J.E., Lemmon, M.T., Rafkin, S.C.R., et al., 2015. Atmospheric movies acquired at the Mars Science Laboratory landing site: cloud morphology, frequency and significance to the gale crater water cycle and phoenix mission results. *Adv. Space Res.* 55, 2217-2238. doi:10.1016/j.asr.2015.02.007.
- Moore, C.A., Moores, J.E., Lemmon, M.T., et al., 2016. A full martian year of line-of-sight extinction within Gale Crater, Mars as acquired by the MSL Navcam through sol 900. *Icarus* 264, 102-108.
- Nelli, S.M., Murphy, J.R., Sprague, A.L., et al., 2007. Dissecting the polar dichotomy of the noncondensable gas enhancement on Mars using the NASA Ames Mars General Circulation Model. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets* 112, E8.
- Rafkin, S.C.R., 2012. The potential importance of non-local, deep transport on the energetics, momentum, chemistry, and aerosol distributions in the atmospheres of Earth, Mars, and Titan. *Planet. Space Sci.* 60 (1), 147-154.
- Rafkin, S.C.R., Michaels, T.I., 2003. Meteorological predictions for 2003 Mars Exploration Rover high-priority landing sites. *J. Geophys. Res.* 108 (E12). doi:10.1029/2002JE002027.
- Rafkin, S.C.R., Sta. Maria, M.R.V., Michaels, T.I., 2002. Simulation of the atmospheric thermal circulation of a martian volcano using a mesoscale numerical model. *Nature* 419 (6908), 697-699.
- Pla-Garcia, J., Rafkin, S.C.R., Kahre, M., et al., 2016. The Meteorology of Gale Crater as Determined from Rover Environmental Monitoring Station Observations and Numerical Modeling. Part I: Comparison of Model Simulations with Observations. *Icarus*, this issue.
- Savijärvi, H., Silli, T., 1993. The Martian slope winds and the nocturnal PBL jet. *J. Atmospheric Sci.* 50 (1), 77-88.
- Serafin, S., Zardi, D., 2010. Structure of the atmospheric boundary layer in the vicinity of a developing upslope flow system: A numerical model study. *J. Atmospheric Sci.* 67 (4), 1171-1185.
- Smith, M.D., 2002. The annual cycle of water vapor on Mars as observed by the thermal emission spectrometer. *J. Geophys. Res.* 107 (E11), 5115.
- Spiga, A., Forget, F., Madeleine, J.-B., et al., 2011. Elements of comparison between Martian and terrestrial mesoscale meteorological phenomena: Katabatic winds and boundary layer convection. *Planet. Space Sci.* 59 (10), 915-922.
- Sprague, A.L., Boynton, W.V., Kerry, K.E., et al., 2004. Mars' South Polar Ar enhancement: A tracer for South Polar seasonal meridional mixing. *Science* 306 (5700), 1364-1367.
- Sprague, A.L., Boynton, W.V., Kerry, K.E., et al., 2007. Mars' atmospheric argon: Tracer for understanding Martian atmospheric circulation and dynamics. *J. Geophys. Res.* 112 (E3), E03S02.
- Sta. Maria, M.R.V., Rafkin, S.C.R., Michaels, T.I., 2006. Numerical simulation of atmospheric bore waves on Mars. *Icarus* 185 (2), 383-394.
- Thomas, P., Veverka, J., Gineris, D., et al., 1984. Dust streaks on Mars. *Icarus* 60 (1), 161-179.
- Thomas, P., Veverka, J., Lee, S., et al., 1981. Classification of wind streaks on Mars. *Icarus* 45 (1), 124-153.
- Toigo, A.D., Richardson, M.I., 2003. Meteorology of proposed Mars Exploration Rover landing sites. *J. Geophys. Res. Planets* 108 (E12).
- Tyler, D., Barnes, J., 2013. Mesoscale modeling of the circulation in the Gale Crater region: An investigation into the complex forcing of convective boundary layer depths. *Mars* 8, 58-77.
- Vasavada, A.R., Chen, A., Barnes, J.R., et al., 2012. Assessment of environments for Mars science laboratory entry, descent, and surface operations. *Space Sci. Rev.* 170 (1-4), 793-835.
- Veverka, J., Gierasch, P., Thomas, P., 1981. Wind streaks on Mars: Meteorological control of occurrence and mode of formation. *Icarus* 45 (1), 154-166.
- Wakimoto, R.M., McElroy, J.L., 1986. Lidar observation of elevated pollution layers over Los Angeles. *J. Clim. Appl. Meteorol.* 25 (11), 1583-1599.
- Webster, C.R., Mahaffy, P.R., Atreya, S.K., et al., 2015. Measurements of Mars methane at Gale Crater by the SAM tunable laser spectrometer on the curiosity rover. *LPI Contributions* 1719, 1366.
- Webster, C.R., Mahaffy, P.R., Atreya, S.K., et al., 2013. Low upper limit to methane abundance on Mars. *Science* 342 (6156), 355-357.
- Whiteman, C.D., 1982. Breakup of temperature inversions in deep mountain valleys: Part I. Observations. *J. Appl. Meteorol.* 21 (3), 270-289.
- Whiteman, C.D., Doran, J.C., 1993. The relationship between overlying synoptic-scale flows and winds within a valley. *J. Appl. Meteorol.* 32 (11), 1669-1682.
- Wilson, R.J., 2000. Evidence for diurnal period Kelvin waves in the Martian atmosphere from Mars Global Surveyor TES data. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 27 (23), 3889-3892.
- Wilson, R.J., Hamilton, K.P., 1996. Comprehensive model simulation of thermal tides in the Martian atmosphere. *J. Atmospheric Sci.* 53, 1290-1326.
- Wolyn, P., McKee, T.B., 1989. Deep stable layers in the Intermountain Western United States. *Mon. Weather Rev.* 117, 461-472.
- Zängl, G., 2005. Dynamical aspects of wintertime cold-air pools in an Alpine valley system. *Mon. Weather Rev.* 113, 2721-2740.